

A Study On Customer Satisfaction Towards Nestle Products with Reference to Tirupur City

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Abstract: Customer satisfaction plays a vital role in determining the success and growth of any company in the competitive consumer goods market. Nestlé is one of the world's leading food and beverage companies, offering a wide range of products such as dairy items, chocolates, beverages, and instant foods. The main objective of this study is to analyze the level of customer satisfaction towards Nestlé products with special reference to Tirupur city. The study focuses on understanding consumer preferences, buying behavior, and the factors influencing satisfaction, including product quality, price, taste, packaging, availability, and brand image. The research is based on primary and secondary data. Primary data were collected from consumers in Tirupur city through a structured questionnaire, while secondary data were gathered from journals, websites, and previous research studies. A descriptive research design was adopted, and tools such as percentage analysis and simple statistical methods were used to interpret the collected data. The findings of the study indicate that most consumers are satisfied with Nestlé products due to their quality, brand reputation, and wide product variety. Factors such as taste, availability, and reasonable pricing significantly influence customer satisfaction and purchasing decisions. The study concludes that maintaining product quality, improving promotional activities, and introducing new product varieties can further enhance customer satisfaction and brand loyalty among consumers. Customer satisfaction is a key driver in retaining customers and strengthening the market position of Nestlé products.

Keywords: Customer Satisfaction, Consumer Preference, Nestlé Products, Buying Behavior, Tirupur City.

I. Introduction

Customer satisfaction measures how customers feel after using a product or obtaining a particular service. Complaint handling, communication, customer expectations, convenience, product value, and product quality determine how satisfied clients are after purchasing a commodity. A brand improves its customer satisfaction when it recognizes the needs of its customers and meets their requirements. Satisfied customers convey various advantages to a business, including improving a business loyalty, trust, attracting more clients through word of mouth, and enabling a firm to increase its sales. Through enhancing quality of life and contributing to a healthier future, they aim to deliver sustainable industry – leading financial performance and earn trust. It has some of the world's most recognizable brands, with household names like Nescafé, global icons like Perrier and local favorites like Nature Nestle and Milo. Customer satisfaction is one of the most important factors that determine the success of any business organization. In today's competitive market environment, customers have a wide range of choices, and their expectations are

continuously increasing. Companies must therefore focus not only on producing quality goods but also on understanding customer needs, preferences, and perceptions. When customers are satisfied, they tend to remain loyal to the brand, recommend it to others, and contribute to long-term business growth.

II. Review Of Literature

Dr.S.Ganesan (2012) The study examined “customer behaviour and brand preference of nestle Maggie noodles. An empirical study with reference to Trichy, Tamilnadu” set out that consumer behavior refers to the behavior that consumers display in searching for Purchasing, using, evaluating and disposing of products and services that they expect, will satisfy their need. This study analyses the brand preference of nestle Maggie noodles by consumers. This study is based on primary data they were collected through interview method by using a structured questionnaire. Necessary data had also been collected from sources like books, magazines and internet.

V.Padmapriya, S.Govindasamy & etal (2013) This research focuses “A Study On Consumer Satisfaction towards nestle baby foods in Salem city” Set out to identify that buyers preference regarding the purchase of nestle baby foods in salem and to analyses the knowledge of the consumers and various attributes like price, quality, quantity and influence of the advertisement etc. They have collected only primary data for their analysis concluded that the marketing of baby food is a potentially promising area ; since the customers are never hesitate to provide the best quality for their children. The health and future of the new generation seem to live in the hands of these manufactures.

Muhammad Amin Khan , Muhammad Raheel & Etal (2014) The study explores “Attitude Of People towards retention and switching : A Study based on Nestle brand in Pakistan “ Published in the Journal of Public Administration and use. The aim of this study is to show the change intention of the people because of totally different multiple factors. The research method of this analysis is descriptive. The keywords used in this study are corporate reputaion, customer loyalty, trust. This Study was focused primarily in a city and therefore the respondents were primarily below the age of thirty. This results of this study shows that client satisfaction and client loyalty have negative impact on switching intention and every factor has positive impact on switching intention.

III. Objectives Of The Study

- To Study the Demographic factor towards usage of Nestle Products.
- To Study the customer satisfaction towards the products of Nestle.
- To analyze the factors influencing the purchase decision of the nestle products.
- To offer suitable suggestions to improve the nestle products.

IV. Statement Of The Problem

Customer report their feelings interest towards the product they use or prefer .The current market is an open market that experiences consumer preferences and tastes changes.When suppliers or businesses determine the best buy products,consumer satisfaction is often employed in marketing and consumer satisfaction scenarios.Nestle’s consumer satisfaction study aimed at finding a solution that would conclude whether customers are satisfied with nestle products or dissatisfied.The description measures how a company’s products or facilities meet customer expectations and is vital for effectively managing a corporation’s customer satisfaction.Firms require representative and reliable satisfaction measures to ensure customers are satisfied.Their gratification gives business owners and marketers the metrics that help them improve and manage their operations.

V. Scope Of The Study

To find how far people are aware and attracted towards the Nestle Products.This study aims how the company satisfies their customer and their influences on buying decisions of selected respondents.The study focuses on selected product categories such as diary items,and instant foods that are commonly available and consumed in the localmarket.It aims to understand customer opinions regarding product quality,taste,price,packaging, To find how far people are aware and attracted towards the Nestle Products.This study aims how the company satisfies their customer and their influences on buying decisions of selected respondents.The study focuses on selected product categories such as diary items,and instant foods availability,and overall brand image.The research also explores factors influencing buying decisions and the extent of brand loyalty among customers.The data for the study is collected from different groups of consumers including students,working professionals,homemakers and business people in Tirupur.The findings are limited to the specific period during which the data is gathered and may not represent opinions outside the selected area of timeframe.Overall,the study provides insights into customer satisfaction levels in Tirupur city and offers suggestions for improving consumer relationships and market performance.

VI. Research Methodology

- **Primary Sources and Secondary Sources :** The Primary Data were collect from the consumers of the nestle products in Tirupur city through structured Questionnaire. The secondary data was collected from publishing by search engine,books,journals,websites and other relevant information.
- **Sample unit :** The Sample unit for the study consists of customers who purchase and use Nestle products in Tirupur city.
- **Sample size :** A total of 100 respondents were selected from Tirupur city representing different age groups,genders and occupations.
- **Sampling Method :** Convenience sampling method was used to collect data from respondents.
- **Statistical tools :** The collected data was analysed using Percentage analysis and Ranking method to understand consumer preferences and influencing factors.

VII. Concept of Nestle Products

In the year 2008 the company launched Nestle Nesvita Pro-Heart Milk with Omega-3 in Mumbai. Nestle Nesvita Pro-Heart is part of daily diet and has Omega-3 heart friendly nutrients scientifically known to help manage cholesterol. As part of their ongoing commitment to offering best in class nutrition products to Indian Consumers the company launched NESTLE NAN 3 a follow-up formula for older infants. During the year MAGGI PICHKOO Tomato ketchup was launched in a unique easy to handle day pack to drive affordability taste and convenience for a larger number of consumers. The company also launched another pioneering product MAGGI Bhuna Masala to cook tasty and healthy everyday meals more conveniently. The company also launched Nestle Kitkat Mini and Nestle Bar One Mini at Rs 3 price to expand the repertoire of offerings. Similarly they launched Nestle Kitkat Chunkey at Rs 15 to strengthen the range of wellness oriented Nestle products that consumers can choose from. The company's three factories were awarded the internationally recognized external certification ISO 14001 for adherence to environmental processes and OSHAS 18001 for Health and safety. With this all the seven factories of the company now have ISO 14001 and ISO 18001 certifications. In the year 2009 the company provided inputs to the group R&D for development of an innovative product Maggi Bhuna Masala.

VIII. Data Analysis And Interpretation

CHART 1

AGE OF THE RESPONDENTS

Interpretation

From the above table 1 is interpreted the Below age 20 of the respondents 45% ,between 21 – 30 ages of the respondents 36%,between 31 – 40 ages of the respondents 13%,Above 40 ages of the respondents 6%.

Hence,45% of the respondents age group Below 20.

TABLE 1
AGE OF THE RESPONDENTS

S.NO	PARTICULARS	NO.OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
1	Below 20	45	45
2	21-30	35	36
3	31-40	14	13
4	Above 40	6	6
	Total	100	100

Source: Primary Data

TABLE 2

MOST INFLUENCING FACTORS IN PURCHASE DECISIONS OF NESTLE PRODUCTS :

S.NO	PARTICULARS	5	4	3	2	1	TOTAL	WEIGHTED AVERAGE	RANK
1	How satisfied are you with the quality of Nestle products?	250	100	39	12	4	405	4.05	I
2	Are you satisfied with the taste?	95	188	57	18	4	362	3.62	III
3	Are you satisfied with product variety?	150	96	81	18	7	352	3.52	IV
4	Are you satisfied with customer service (if any issue arises)?	115	148	39	28	11	341	3.41	VI
5	Are you satisfied with promotional offers?	170	148	24	18	10	370	3.7	II
6	Overall satisfaction level towards Nestle products	145	128	39	30	8	350	3.5	V

Source: Primary Data

CHART 2

MOST INFLUENCING FACTORS IN PURCHASE DECISION OF NESTLE PRODUCTS

Interpretation

From the above table 2 weighted average analysis, Among the factors, quality of Nestle products has the highest weighted average (4.05) and is ranked first, indicating that most respondents are highly satisfied with the quality. Promotional offers (3.7) are ranked second, followed by taste (3.62) in third place. Product variety (3.52) and overall satisfaction (3.5) are ranked fourth and fifth respectively. Customer service (3.41) has the lowest weighted average and is ranked sixth, showing comparatively lower satisfaction among respondents.

IX. FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

The findings reveal that a majority of the respondents (47%) belong to the age group of Below 20 years and 56% are female, indicating the young customers, especially women, form a major part of the sample. Regarding the satisfied with quality of nestle products (4.05) ranked first, indicating that most respondents are highly satisfied with the quality. Promotional offers (3.7) are ranked second, followed by taste (3.62) in third place. Product variety (3.52) and overall satisfaction (3.5) are ranked fourth and fifth respectively. Customer service (3.41) has the lowest weighted average and is ranked sixth, showing comparatively lower satisfaction among respondents.

X. Suggestions

- Nestle should maintain consistent taste, quality, and freshness in all its products to increase customer satisfaction and loyalty.
- The company can launch more innovative flavours and healthy product options to attract different age groups and changing consumer preferences.
- Nestle products should be priced competitively so that customers from all income groups can afford them.
- The company should ensure that all products are easily available in supermarkets, small retail stores, and online platforms in Tirupur city.
- Attractive, eco-friendly, and informative packaging can improve the customer experience and create a positive brand image.
- Nestle can use social media, advertisements, and offers to create more awareness and attract new customers.

XI. Conclusion

The study on customer satisfaction towards the products of Nestle with reference to Tirupur concludes that most consumers are satisfied with the quality, taste, and availability of Nestle products. The findings reveal that customers prefer Nestle products because of their trusted brand name, consistent quality, and wide variety of food and beverage items. Many respondents purchase these products frequently and show a positive attitude towards the brand. However, a few consumers feel that the price of some products is slightly high when compared to other brands. Overall, the study indicates that Nestle has successfully built strong customer loyalty and satisfaction in Tirupur city, and by maintaining product quality and reasonable pricing, the company can further strengthen its market position and customer in the future.

References

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